

DETERMINATION OF KINETIC PARAMETERS ASSOCIATED WITH THE CURING OF THERMOSET
RESINS USING DIELECTRIC AND DSC DATA

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ABSTRACT

Traditionally, the kinetic parameters associated with the curing of thermoset resins have been determined using Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC), and some recent studies have looked at the use of dielectric data for the determination of these parameters. To estimate these parameters, the appropriate kinetic rate equation in terms of the degree of cure is chosen for the particular resin in question, and the rate constants are determined for experiments conducted at different temperatures. Assuming an Arrhenius relationship with temperature, activation energy constants can be calculated from the rate constants associated with each different experimental temperature.

In this study, kinetic parameters were estimated for a bisphenol-A-diglycidylether/meta-phenylenediamine system from the results of both DSC and dielectric experiments. Three different kinetic models were assumed, and the parameters associated with each of the models were estimated from both types of experimental data. Good agreement was found between most of the parameters estimated using different experimental data sets for each kinetic model. The results from the estimates of the parameter associated with the third kinetic model investigated indicated that this model might be inadequate in describing the curing reaction for the epoxy system under investigation.

KEYWORDS: Cure Cycle; Matrix/Epoxy; Neat Resin; Test Method; Kinetics

1. INTRODUCTION

The accurate determination of kinetic parameters associated with the curing of epoxy matrix composite materials is important in the development and control of fabrication processes. The most commonly used method of determining these parameters involves the use of differential scanning calorimetry (DSC). One difficulty with this method is that small sample sizes (approximately 10 mg) are required, for which the insurance of homogeneity might be difficult if fiber reinforced composite samples rather than neat epoxy samples are tested. An alternate method involves the use of dielectric analysis for which large sample sizes can be used; however, this

method lacks the wide spread use and acceptability associated with the DSC method.

The objectives of this study were related to the estimation and the comparison of the kinetic parameters associated with the curing of a thermoset resin from both DSC and dielectric experiments. Bisphenol-A-diglycidylether (BADGE)/meta-phenylenediamine (mPDA) was the thermoset epoxy resin under consideration. The specific objectives were: 1) to conduct isothermal and dynamic DSC and dielectric experiments to obtain degree of cure as a function of curing time; 2) to estimate the kinetic parameters associated with three different kinetic models previously used to describe the cure kinetics of this material from both DSC and dielectric experimental data; and, 3) to compare the results of the parameters estimated using different experimental procedures.

Differential scanning calorimetry has seen wide spread use by many researchers in the estimation of kinetic parameters associated with the curing of thermoset resins (1,2,3,4,5). Previously, power compensation and heat flux mode differential scanning calorimeters were used in separate studies; both types of calorimeters were used in this study. In contrast to DSC, there has been relatively little use of dielectric experiments for the estimation of kinetic parameters (6,7) or for comparative analysis between DSC and dielectric studies (8). This study involves both the comparison of results from different types of differential scanning calorimeters and the comparison of results from DSC and dielectric experiments.

2. THEORETICAL CONSIDERATIONS

2.1 Kinetic Models Several different kinetic models have been used to characterize curing in the BADGE/mPDA system; in this study, kinetic parameters were estimated for three of these models. The BADGE/MPDA resin is an amine-epoxy system, and it is often characterized as a system for which the reaction rate is accelerated due to autocatalyztion. One model used to analyze this and other BADGE based epoxy systems contains two rate constants to describe curing, assuming a combined (m+n)th order, autocatalyzed reaction rate mechanism as shown below.

$$\frac{d\alpha}{dt} = (c_1 + c_2\alpha^m) (1-\alpha)^n \quad (1)$$

In this equation, α is the degree of cure (fraction conversion), t is time, c_1 is the first rate constant which represents nth order kinetics, c_2 is the second rate constant which represents the autocatalytic nature of the reaction, and m and n are constants. Equation (1) was used by Ryan and Dutta (1) to describe curing in a BADGE-MPDA epoxy system assuming $m+n=2$. This equation was also used by Sourour and Kamal (9), but with m and n restricted such that $m=n=1$. In both of these studies, the rate constants c_1 and c_2 were estimated from isothermal DSC experimental data, and an Arrhenius relationship was assumed between the rate constants and temperature; this relationship can be mathematically described as

$$c_i = A_i \exp(-E_i/RT) \quad i=1,2 \quad (2)$$

where T is absolute temperature, R is the gas constant, and the parameters to be estimated are the activation energy constants, E_i , and the pre-exponential factors, A_i .

Kamal et al. (1) estimated the Arrhenius parameters from isothermal and dynamic DSC experiments for a BADGE-amine epoxy system using eq. (1) with $m=1$ and $n=2$, as shown below.

$$\frac{d\alpha}{dt} = (c_1 + c_2\alpha)(1-\alpha)^2 \quad (3)$$

They found eq. (3) followed experimental results for α up to 50%; at that time, the experimental data indicated that diffusion controlled the reaction rate. Likewise, this model was used by Lee et al. (11) in studying Hercules 3501-6 resin; in this case, they found that the reaction was diffusion controlled for $\alpha > 30\%$.

A simpler equation was used by Prime (12) to describe curing in the BADGE/MPDA system which incorporated both isothermal and dynamic DSC experiments. In this model, an n th order reaction is assumed with no autocatalyztion ($c_2 = 0$):

$$\frac{d\alpha}{dt} = c_1(1-\alpha)^n \quad (4)$$

Equation (4) was also used in the analysis of curing of a BADGE resin from dielectric experimental data (6).

2.2 DSC Analysis The underlying assumption in utilizing DSC data for kinetic analysis is that the heat of reaction is proportional to the reaction rate. The heat of reaction is measured directly in DSC experiments, and the degree of cure rate is determined from the heat of reaction and the total heat of reaction, as shown below.

$$\frac{d\alpha}{dt} = \frac{H(t)}{H_t} \quad (5)$$

where $H(t)$ is the heat of reaction at time, t , and H_t is the total heat of reaction from dynamic DSC experiments, given by

$$H_t = \int_0^{t_0} H(t) dt \quad (6)$$

where t_0 is the total curing time. Dynamic DSC experiments are those in which the temperature is increases linearly with time throughout the entire cure.

The kinetic models discussed in the previous section (eqs. (1), (3), and (4)) require $\alpha(t)$ in addition to $d\alpha/dt$. The degree of cure, α , can be found through the integration of eq. (6) over t :

$$\alpha(t) = \frac{\int_0^t H(t) dt}{H_t} \quad (7)$$

The integral in eq. (7) is typically evaluated numerically using DSC system software.

2.3 Dielectric Analysis The analysis of cure from dielectric data was based on the classic Debye equations describing dielectric response (7). These equations relate the permittivity and the loss factor of the material with angular frequency. The equation relating the loss factor and angular frequency can be written as:

$$\varepsilon''/\varepsilon_0\omega = \sigma + \left[\frac{(\varepsilon_r - \varepsilon_u)\omega^2\varepsilon_0\tau}{(1 + (\omega\tau)^2)} \right] \quad (8)$$

where ε'' is the loss factor, ω is the angular frequency, σ is ionic conductivity, τ is the characteristic relaxation time, and ε_r , ε_u , and ε_0 are the relaxed, unrelaxed, and free space permittivities, respectively.

The ionic conductivity term in eq. (8) is of interest in analyzing the cure kinetics of thermoset resins. The ionic conductivity is inversely related to viscosity, and the logarithm of the ionic conductivity is linearly related to the degree of cure (7). The second term on the right-hand side of eq. (8) represents the dipole influence, and it is frequency dependent. The ionic conductivity can be found by plotting the left-hand side of eq. (8) with respect to curing time for different frequencies; the regions of superimposing data represent the ionic conductivity influence, and the regions of no superimposition represent the frequency dependent dipole influence (7). In the analysis of cure kinetics, the frequency dependent portion of the data is disregarded, and the remaining data represent the ionic conductivity as a function of time.

The degree of cure is found from the logarithm of the ionic conductivity as a function of time and the logarithm of the ionic conductivity evaluated at 0% and 100% cure:

$$\alpha = \frac{\log(\sigma) - \log(\sigma)_{0\% \text{cure}}}{\log(\sigma)_{100\% \text{cure}} - \log(\sigma)_{0\% \text{cure}}} \quad (9)$$

where $\log(\sigma)_{0\% \text{cure}}$ and $\log(\sigma)_{100\% \text{cure}}$ are the logarithms of the ionic conductivity at 0% cure and 100% cure, respectively.

2.4 Estimation of Parameters Different methods have been used in the estimation of the rate constants and exponentials in eqs. (1), (3), and (4). Ryan and Dutta (1) describe in detail one method to determine the parameters c_1 , c_2 , and m in eq. (1). In this method, the first rate constant, c_1 , is evaluated at $t=0$, and then the second rate constant, c_2 , is expressed in terms of c_1 , m , and the maximum degree of cure rate, α_p (defined as α at the time when $d^2\alpha/dt^2 = 0$). The expression for α_p is substituted into eq. (1) (with $m+n=2$), resulting in the following implicit expression for m (1):

$$m \ln(\alpha_p) = \ln \left(\frac{\left(\frac{d\alpha}{dt} \right)_{\alpha=\alpha_p}}{(1-\alpha_p)^{2-m}} - c_1 \right) - \ln \left(\frac{(2-m)c_1\alpha_p^{1-m}}{m-2\alpha_p} \right) \quad (10)$$

This procedure requires α and $d\alpha/dt$ to be evaluated at only two times: at $t=0$ and at the time when $d\alpha/dt$ is a maximum. Some disadvantages of this method are that not all of the DSC data are utilized and the data utilized at the initial time are often prone to experimental errors in isothermal tests (13).

The kinetic model in eq.(3) was used by Sourour and Kamal (9) to describe curing in a BADGE epoxy system. The parameters, c_1 and c_2 , were estimated by rearranging the kinetic equation so that the right-hand side of the equation is linear in α , as shown below.

$$\frac{d\alpha/dt}{(1-\alpha)^2} = c_1 + c_2\alpha \quad (11)$$

The rate constants were then determined from a linear regression analysis of the expression of the left-hand side of eq. (9) and α . This procedure is relatively easy to implement, and it utilizes all of the DSC data. This procedure can also be utilized in estimating the parameters in eq. (1). If eq. (1) is rearranged as follows:

$$\frac{d\alpha/dt}{(1-\alpha)^{2-m}} = c_1 + c_2\alpha^m \quad (12)$$

c_1 , c_2 , and m can be determined using an iterative-linear regression estimation procedure (13). Alternatively, m can be set equal to a specific value (e.g., 1) and then c_1 and c_2 can be determined linear regression only.

The parameters associated with the third model (eq. (4)) can be estimated by first taking the natural logarithm of eq. (4) and then using linear regression to estimate $\ln(c_1)$ and n (13). Similarly, the parameters associated with the Arrhenius relationship shown in eq. (2) can be estimated from values for the rate constants at different temperatures by first taking the natural logarithm of eq. (2) and then using linear regression to estimate the parameters E_i and $\ln(A_i)$.

3. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

3.1 DSC Experiments Two independent experimental studies were conducted using BADGE (Epon 828, Shell Chemical Comp.)/mpDA epoxy resin. The first study was conducted using a heat flux mode DSC (Dupont Instruments 910 DSC cell), and a second independent study was conducted using a power compensation mode DSC (Perkin Elmer DSC 7). After mixing the resin and the curing agent in a one to one equivalency ratio, the liquid mixture was placed in DSC pans, which were then sealed and weighed in preparation for dynamic or isothermal DSC experiments. (The dynamic experiments were used to determine H_t (eq. (6)), and the isothermal experiments were conducted to obtain $H(t)$ for each experimental temperature.)

In the first study using the DuPont DSC, dynamic scans were performed at 5°C/min from room temperature to 220°C, and isothermal scans were performed at 60°C, 70°C, 100°C, and 110°C. The isothermal temperatures studied were determined using the procedure described by (14). In the experiments conducted using the Perkin Elmer DSC, dynamic scans were conducted at 4°C/min from room temperature to 200°C, and isothermal scans were conducted at 70°C,

80°C, 120°C, and 130°C. This represents the temperature range used in previous DSC studies by other researchers for this type of epoxy (15).

3.2 Dielectric Experiments Isothermal dielectric experiments were conducted at 70°C, 80°C, 120°C, and 130°C using an Eumetric® System II Microdielectrometer (Micromet Instruments, Inc.). In each experiment, five frequencies were used. In the 80°C, 120°C, and 130°C isothermal experiments, frequencies at 1000 Hz, 100 Hz, 10 Hz, 1 Hz, and 0.1 Hz were used, and in the 70°C isothermal experiment, frequencies at 1000 Hz, 100 Hz, 10 Hz, 1 Hz, and 0.07 Hz were used. Upon the conclusion of each experiment, $\log(\epsilon''\epsilon_0\omega)$ for each frequency was plotted versus curing time, and the region of superimposed data was identified using the Eumetric® System II software.

To determine the degree of cure from eq. (9), the $\log(\sigma)_{0\%cure}$ and the $\log(\sigma)_{100\%cure}$ were also needed. The $\log(\sigma)_{0\%cure}$ was found from the initial data points from each of the isothermal runs; these points corresponded in all cases. The $\log(\sigma)_{100\%cure}$ value was found from the log conductivity values at the end of dynamic dielectric experiments.

4. RESULTS

The kinetic parameters associated with each of the kinetic models discussed previously (eqs. (1), (3), and (4)) were estimated from experimental data from the two DSC's and the microdielectrometer. The degree of cure and the degree of cure rate were first determined from the isothermal and dynamic DSC and dielectric data. Plotting the left-hand side of eqs. (11) and (12) with respect to α and α^m , respectively, demonstrated that the end portion of the cure cycle (e.g., $\alpha > 0.6$) did not follow any of the kinetic models and another mechanism, such as diffusion, controlled the reaction rate. Therefore, the kinetic parameters associated with eqs. (1), (3), and (4) were estimated using data from the first portion of the cure cycle only (e.g., $\alpha < 0.6$).

4.1 Estimation of the Kinetic Parameters Associated with Eq. (1) The rate constants, c_1 and c_2 , and the exponential, m , were first estimated for each of the isothermal experiments using the DuPont 910 DSC. These parameters were estimated using both the technique described by Ryan and Dutta (1) and the iterative-linear regression scheme (13) discussed previously. The mean and associated 95% confidence intervals for c_1 , c_2 , and m for each of the experimental temperatures using the two estimation procedures are shown in Table 1. The mean values were determined from a minimum of three repetitions at each temperature.

The estimated values for the exponential, m , shown in Table 1 were all less than one, while the value of m estimated for the same epoxy system by Ryan and Dutta (1) was 1.06. In addition, Kamal et al. (10) estimated the kinetic parameters associated with eq. (1) assuming $m = 1$; therefore, the remaining experimental data from the Perkin Elmer DSC and the Micromet Microdielectrometer were analyzed assuming $m = 1$. The rate constants were estimated from these data using the kinetic model in the form of eq. (12) with $m = 1$ and linear regression. The rate constants were assumed in each case to follow an Arrhenius relationship with temperature (eq. (2)). The estimated E_i and $\ln(A_i)$ values and the associated confidence intervals from the DuPont DSC data, the Perkin Elmer DSC data, and the dielectric data are shown in

TABLE 1. ESTIMATED RATE CONSTANTS, c_1 AND c_2 , AND EXPONENTIAL, m , ASSOCIATED WITH EQ. (1).

Temp. ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	c_1 (s^{-1})	c_2 (s^{-1})	m	Comments
60	(2.7 \pm 1.7)E-5	(3.6 \pm 0.3)E-4	0.80 \pm 0.05	Ryan and Dutta Method (1)
70	(5.2 \pm 2.2)E-5	(5.8 \pm 1.1)E-4	0.82 \pm 0.06	
100	(2.6 \pm 0.7)E-4	(2.3 \pm 0.4)E-3	0.74 \pm 0.04	
110	(3.9 \pm 1.9)E-4	(3.7 \pm 0.3)E-3	0.72 \pm 0.16	
60	(2.0 \pm 1.0)E-5	(2.3 \pm 0.3)E-4	0.82 \pm 0.07	Iteration - Linear Regression Method (13)
70	(4.3 \pm 2.4)E-5	(3.8 \pm 0.9)E-4	0.85 \pm 0.08	
100	(1.6 \pm 0.3)E-4	(1.5 \pm 0.2)E-3	0.73 \pm 0.09	
110	(3.2 \pm 0.5)E-4	(2.4 \pm 0.4)E-3	0.73 \pm 0.18	

Table 2, along with the estimated parameters from Ryan and Dutta (1) and Kamal et al. (10).

4.2 Estimation of the Kinetic Parameters Associated with Eqs. (3) and (4)
The rate constants associated with eq. (3) were estimated from each of the isothermal experiments using the DuPont DSC, the Perkin Elmer DSC, and the Eumetric[®] Microdielectrometer. The rate constants and the activation energy constants and pre-exponential factors were estimated as described in Section 2.4. The results for the activation energy constants and the intercept, $\ln(A_1)$, along with the 95% confidence intervals from the two DSC studies and the dielectric studies, are also shown in Table 2. In addition, the results of the study by Sourour and Kamal (9) are given.

The rate constant, c_1 , and the exponential, n , in eq. (4) were estimated for each of the DSC data sets and the dielectric data set. The Arrhenius parameters were then estimated from the estimated values for c_1 . The results for E_1 , $\ln(A_1)$, and n for the three data sets are also shown in Table 2, along with results from Prime (12).

5. DISCUSSION

The parameter estimates from the first kinetic model (eq. (1)) are considered first. The results from Table 2 show that the confidence intervals for E_1 , E_2 , $\ln(A_1)$, and $\ln(A_2)$ from each of the experimental data sets in this study overlap one another, indicating that statically, the means are equivalent. With the exception of the estimates of E_1 , the estimated mean values of the parameter estimates given by (1) and (10) fall within the confidence intervals of the estimates in this study. In addition, if the values of E_1 given by (1) and (10) have confidence intervals on the same order as the smallest of those found in this study (i.e. ± 5.8 kJ/mole), these means would also be equivalent.

The confidence intervals for E_1 and $\ln(A_1)$ associated with eq. (1) are consistently larger than the intervals for E_2 and $\ln(A_2)$. This is to be

TABLE 2. ESTIMATED ACTIVATION ENERGY CONSTANTS, E_1 AND E_2 , AND PRE-EXPONENTIAL VALUES, A_1 AND A_2 .

Model Eq. #	Experiment type	E_1 (kJ/mole)	E_2 (kJ/mole)	$\ln(A_1)$ $\ln(s^{-1})$	$\ln(A_2)$ $\ln(s^{-1})$	Exponent	Reference
(1)	Isothermal	57.4±6.3	50.4±2.9	10.2±2.1	10.2±0.9	m=.77±.03	this study ^a
	Isothermal	55.8±5.8	49.2±2.1	9.4±2.0	9.4±0.7	m=.78±.04	this study ^b
	Isothermal	64.9±12.1	45.4±6.2	12.7±3.9	8.1±2.0	m=1	this study ^c
	Isothermal	58.2±34.6	39.1±17.7	10.5±11.2	5.9±5.8	m=1	this study ^d
	Isothermal	65	46	11.8	not given	m=1.06	(1)
	Isothermal	62	48	10.6	9.1	m=1	(10)
(2)	Isothermal	64.5±4.9	50.6±2.0	12.1±1.7	10.6±0.7		this study ^e
	Isothermal	68.2±16.2	51.1±4.7	12.9±5.2	10.7±1.5		this study ^c
	Isothermal	31.7±6.6	44.6±2.1	1.23±2.1	8.7±0.7		this study ^d
	Isothermal	81	48	16.0	9.5		(9)
(3)	Isothermal	56.1±4.9		16.2±0.8		n=-1.0±.1	this study ^e
	Isothermal	65.2±10.3		13.0±3.3		n=-1.8±2.1	this study ^c
	Isothermal	49.8±10.7		7.9±3.5		n=-1.5±1.0	this study ^d
	Dynamic	50-63		8-12		n=-0.9±1.3	(12)

a. Parameters estimated from DuPont DSC data; Ryan and Dutta method (1).

b. Parameters estimated from DuPont DSC data; iteration-linear regression method (13).

c. Parameters estimated from Perkin Elmer DSC data.

d. Parameters estimated from Dielectric data.

e. Parameters estimated from DuPont DSC data.

expected since E_1 and $\ln(A_1)$ are dominate at the initial portion of the cure cycle (note that $\alpha/dt=c_1$ at $t=0$) at the time when experimental errors in isothermal experiments can be expected to be the greatest (13). (In estimating the parameters from the kinetic model shown in eq. (1), it is assumed that the sample undergoes a step change in temperature at $t=0$, while in an actual experiment, this change has a finite duration.)

The confidence intervals of the parameter estimates associated with eq. (1) from the dielectric data are very large compared to those obtained from the DSC data. This suggests that the experimental variability of the dielectric data is much higher than that of the DSC data. Even so, the mean estimates of E_1 and $\ln(A_1)$ are close to the means of the associated parameters estimates from the DSC studies. However, the differences between the parameter estimates for E_2 and $\ln(A_2)$ from the DSC and dielectric data are relatively much higher. This might reflect the fundamental differences between the assumptions used the DSC and dielectric analysis. The parameter estimates from the dielectric data consistently predict that α has less temperature dependence (E_1 and E_2 are lower) and that the reaction rate is lower at any

given temperature ($\ln(A_1)$ and $\ln(A_2)$ are lower) than that predicted by the DSC results. This might indicate that the measurement of heat flow might be more a sensitive means of determining degree of cure than the dielectric loss factor.

The parameters associated with eq. (3) shown in Table 2 estimated from the two sets of DSC data showed good agreement in all cases. However, with the exception of the estimate for $\ln(A_2)$, the parameter estimates from the dielectric data were significantly lower than the parameters estimated from the DSC data. The results for E_2 and $\ln(A_2)$ presented by reference (9) fall within or are very close to the confidence intervals of the results of the DSC experiments in the study. However, the results for E_1 and $\ln(A_1)$ from (9) are within the confidence intervals for the Perkin-Elmer DSC results, but they are significantly higher than those from the DuPont and the dielectric data. This again suggests that the first rate constant (c_1) is more difficult to estimate than c_2 .

Comparing the confidence intervals of E_1 , E_2 , $\ln(A_1)$, and $\ln(A_2)$ associated with eq. (1) from the DSC results with the same parameters associated with eq. (3) shows that the corresponding means for each parameter are equivalent. This suggests that the differences in the order of reaction between eqs. (1) and (3) do not have an effect on the magnitudes of the activation energy constants or the pre-exponential factors.

The parameters estimated by Prime (12) for eq. (4) fall within the corresponding confidence intervals shown in Table 2 for E_1 from this study. The confidence intervals for $\ln(A_i)$ from the Perkin-Elmer DSC study, the dielectric data, and reference (12) overlap one another, but the value from the DuPont DSC data is significantly higher. The estimated values for n from this study differ greatly than those given by (12); for the kinetic model to be appropriate, a positive value of n is expected. The values of n in this study were all found to be negative indicating that the model might be inappropriate for this particular epoxy system.

6. CONCLUSIONS

The conclusions drawn from this study are:

1. The estimates for the kinetic parameters, E_1 and A_1 , associated with the rate constant c_1 in eqs. (1) and (2) from isothermal DSC and dielectric experiments have greater variability than those associated with c_2 .
2. The mean parameter estimates resulting from the dielectric experiments were lower than those estimated from DSC data (with the exception of E_1 and $\ln(A_1)$ from c_1 in eq. (1)), although in many cases the associated confidence intervals overlapped.
3. There was no significant difference between corresponding kinetic parameters estimated from the DuPont and the Perkin-Elmer DSC experiments for any of the kinetic models tested (eqs. (1), (3), and (4)).
4. There was no significant difference between the activation energy constants and pre-exponential factors associated with eq. (1) estimated from either of the DSC studies and the corresponding parameters estimated for the kinetic model shown in eq. (3).
5. The prediction of a negative exponential for the third kinetic model (eq.

(4)) is an indication that this model might not adequately describe the actual kinetics of the curing reaction.

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